

DEVELOPMENT OF CADETS' SKILLS IN WORKING WITH OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS IN MILITARY DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS

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One of the essential characteristics of the professional activity of modern specialists in all industries is a large flow of information, which predetermines the need to have the skills to work with it and develop the ability of the subject of activity to critically perceive its content. Cadets, as future officers, need these skills to perform the tasks of military service and develop the ability to optimally use a large amount of data in their work activities, both in standard and non-standard situations.

Development of cadets' skills in working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations. When interacting with the information environment, a serviceman is a key link in the chain "receipt of information - analysis - processing - transmission", performing the functions of both a communicator and a recipient. This determines the requirements for the formation and development of cadets' skills in working with information data and the ability to treat them professionally and correctly [1]. The information environment is becoming more and more voluminous, but it is often saturated with outdated or insignificant, often unreliable, negative, deliberately distorted and even provocative information. The development of skills in working with information in these conditions acquires practical significance due to its influence on the consciousness of military personnel and their life activity [3]. The specifics of a serviceman's activity determine the richness of the professional information environment, the volume and content of the diverse data with which he operates. The use of various elements of working with official documents in training military personnel carries significant potential for developing their skills in searching, collecting and processing information, practical application of data and their various combinations.

Concepts that reflect the essence of information support for professional activities, as well as the development of cadets' skills in working with official documents, occupy increasingly significant positions and express the degree of dependence of its effectiveness on the individual's ability to perform various transformative actions and operations with initial data and documents. Any activity takes place in a specific information environment, which is interpreted

as a body of knowledge, facts and information, not formalized in the form of an information system, used by a certain number of subjects. All components are in a relationship of mutual influence, determine the level of influence of a given information environment on others that exist and develop as elements of information structures of a higher order - the professional community, society, etc. Professional activity of working with official documents of a cadet requires stable skills in working with a large volume of information materials, various source data that need to be analyzed, summarized, systematized and structured. This is an important stage of decision-making in the implementation of organizational and managerial functions of official interaction. Working with information begins with understanding the problem. This process represents the involvement of a serviceman in the decision-making process to perform certain professional actions and includes a clear understanding of the purpose of the planned actions, their meaning and significance; the plan of the senior superior and the content of the task assigned to him; the role of your unit (military collective) in the planned actions; possible subjects of interaction and their potential role; the form and timing of presenting the results of the completed task of working with official documents [3].

The development of cadets' skills in working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations creates a new information product (new knowledge, a new description of the action algorithm, etc.), integrating initial data and some data from other information systems. The form and content of this product reflect the subject's understanding of the nature and properties of data connections, their essence, priority, purpose and influence on the development of theory and practice in a certain social environment. During the analysis of a large amount of information on a certain topic, the student finds himself in conditions where the assimilation of the material does not occur spontaneously, on the basis of the specific functioning of mental processes, but is carried out through the conscious selection of those data that, according to a particular individual, are significant and justified.

The most promising in developing the skills of working with official documents of cadets seem to be various types of independently performed analyzes, which are the result of processing information data that makes up an artificially generated information environment for solving a specific task (task, order or instruction, demonstration of some action). In addition, the search for ways to enhance the cognitive activity of cadets, developing a high level of independence and creativity in them during practice led to the development of

cadets' skills in working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations as one of the most promising [1].

Skills in working with official documents include a training system in which the knowledge, skills and abilities of students are formed in the process of planning and performing gradually more complex practical actions based on tasks to create a new product of a given type. A feature of working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations is its focus on the active independent work of students for a certain time, taking into account the specific requirements for learning outcomes and the conditions of the educational environment. This approach is organically integrated into group methods and forms of training at a military university. And although the majority of modern scientists and teaching practitioners are convinced that at the level of professional training, skills in working with official documents have a positive impact on the quality of training of future specialists [2].

There are a number of conditions for the successful development of cadets' skills in working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations: a clearly formulated socially significant problem, the solution of which requires integrated knowledge and the ability to research a solution; creation of organizational and methodological conditions for independent activities of cadets (methodological recommendations, access to information sources and technical means); specific requirements for content, type, type, form, etc. are determined. Modern scientists note that the information flow today is so powerful and dynamic that regulated measures are required in this direction, defining a differentiated approach to sources of information; timely informing personnel about the media disseminating negative, unfounded, and false information; the need to develop among military personnel the skills of critical assessment of facts, events, data presented to the public, taking into account the interests of state security [2]. When developing cadets' skills in working with official documents in military-diplomatic relations, it is advisable to take into account knowledge, analysis skills and moral and psychological aspects of the influence of information on a person's consciousness, and therefore on his professional actions.

Thus, the development of skills in working with information and official documents of cadets of military universities is the process of becoming one of the important elements of professional training, ensuring the ability not only to use some data when performing official duties, but also to operate with current

true information and facts in the interests of effective performance of personal composition of service and combat missions.

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